

PROBLEMS OF ASSIGNING LEXEMES OF PARFUM IN MODERN ELECTRONIC THESAURUS DICTIONARIES

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Abstract: The principles of giving of Parfum lexemes in explanatory dictionaries in English and Uzbek languages were studied. The instability of the use of some Parfum lexemes in electronic dictionaries shows that there is work to be done in this regard as well. The problems of providing terms related to parfum in modern electronic thesaurus dictionaries were considered. In this article, the shortcomings of assigning lexical units to the field of parfum in modern electronic thesaurus dictionaries were reviewed.

Keywords: Parfum lexemes, electronic dictionaries, Thesaurus, Concept, lexicography.

Introduction. With the advent of computer technology, software developers created a new type of dictionary - electronic. An electronic dictionary is a dictionary on a computer or other electronic device. Allows you to find frequently, taking into account the ability to search for morphology and phrases, as well as the ability to change the direction of translation. This type of dictionary is a completely new word in the history of lexicography and marks a new qualitative stage in its development. Currently, electronic dictionaries are emerging from the shadow of paper dictionaries, becoming independent players on the language platform, and players who may in the near future turn other characters into exhibits of the Museum of the Book. After all, electronic dictionaries have a number of clear and important advantages over dictionaries, which is why their availability is limited. The creation of convenient, modern electronic dictionaries in the field of linguistics is the proof of our opinion. Thesaurus dictionaries, Wordnet dictionaries, translation dictionaries, multilingual electronic dictionaries all serve as the basis of machine translation. The above-mentioned dictionaries were created in Western linguistics and are being developed in line with the times. Several works have been done in world linguistics to create dictionaries of this type. In particular, there are many electronic online dictionaries of this type on the Internet. One of them is the thesaurus dictionary.

Thesaurus is a general or special dictionary that shows semantic relations between lexical units - homonyms, synonyms, antonyms, paronyms, hyponyms, hyperonyms and other concepts in modern linguistics, and is a special type of such dictionaries. Unlike other dictionaries, this dictionary is an ideographic dictionary that reflects the semantic relations between lexical units related to a field of science or such units placed in a subject. In it, the necessary words are searched according to the concept.

Theoretically, thesaurus is one of the possible models of the lexical-semantic system. In practice, it is used as an individual dictionary enrichment and quick search tool. In this sense, the thesaurus was considered the opposite of a dictionary. Usually, when looking for the meaning of a word, but not the word itself, thesauruses are used. That is, although the concept is known here, information is obtained about the group of words or word forms under this concept. It may be in the system, but we may not know what the word itself is. Therefore, as stated in the sources, the thesaurus is a dictionary and serves as a storehouse for words. Thesaurus is a dictionary that covers all the words in a particular language and fully reflects their usage in the text. Dictionaries based on collecting lexical units from specific written monuments (for example, compiled in Greek, Latin languages) are such dictionaries. Dictionaries compiled according to are also a thesaurus. It serves for lexical-semantic, corporate communication (understanding of individuals related to each other through the same science or profession).

Materials and methods Thesauruses are one of the important tools in the interpretation of a certain science. If we take the concept of thesaurus together with the above qualities as a type of dictionary, then we can make a comparative opinion as follows: Although both the concepts of dictionary and thesaurus serve to know words and their meanings, but about their word meanings. The methods of providing information are different, that is, they differ from each other. While the dictionary is mostly used by language learners to determine the meanings, pronunciation and orthography of words, the thesaurus is used by researchers to find synonyms, antonyms, homonyms and other meaning forms of words. it is used to find.. It also provides comprehensive information about other words that are the same as the word being referenced. Most researchers use a thesaurus to find synonyms, antonyms, paronyms, and the like. Usually, the thesaurus does not depend much on the origin of words in the language, in particular, it does not provide additional information about the etymology of words.

Results and discussions. We may encounter several problems when entering terms related to the field of acting, as well as entering terms from other fields into the thesaurus dictionaries. First of all, it is necessary to get acquainted with the requirements for entering terms in thesaurus dictionaries with the help of a human hand and with the help of an automated system.

Problems of giving terms in thesaurus dictionaries

Step	Concept	Manual system	Automated system
Determining the scope of the topic	Determining the topic of the field where the thesaurus is being created	Approach with intellectual actions	Approach with intellectual actions
Selecting appropriate terms to describe the domain	Collecting a sufficient number of domain concepts to be included in the Thesaurus	Manual selection	Computational selection and ranking list preparation using statistical methods
Deciding on the precise form of vocabulary terms	Determining acceptable grammatical forms (plural or singular forms, pronunciation, abbreviations, acronyms)	Adhering to thesaurus construction and development standards	Adhering to thesaurus construction and development standards
Organizing terms in a useful way	Linking a reflective relationship with dominant concepts	A manual approach requiring intellectual effort	Based on a statistical and syntactic framework
Display terms in a useful way	Alphabetize terms	Use manual techniques such as card systems Computerized	Use manual techniques such as card systems Computerized

According to this table, we can get acquainted with the stages and problems of placing words in thesaurus dictionaries, both electronically and by human hand. According to the problems given above, we tried to study the issues of providing lexical units related to the field of art in modern electronic thesaurus dictionaries. During the study of various dictionaries, we witnessed that there is no thesaurus dictionary in the Uzbek language related to the field of art.

We also studied the problems of providing terms related to the field of art in the thesaurus dictionaries available in English. In doing so, we studied various differences and encountered problems in giving authorship terms in "Macmillan",

"Cambridge", "Merriam webster", "Wordnet english dictionary", and "Longman" English dictionary and thesaurus.

Differences in giving authorial terms in English thesaurus dictionaries

Longman	Sorry, no results for “cream” with English
Cambridge	a <u>soft substance</u> that you <u>rub</u> into <u>your skin</u> : <u>face/hand</u> cream moisturizing cream Put some <u>sun</u> cream on to <u>protect your face</u>
Merriam webster	Sorry, no results for “cream” with English
Macmillan	thick substance put on skin
Wordnet	Sorry, no results for “cream” with English

The above table shows the use of the word "cream" in various electronic thesaurus dictionaries. Not only in this word, but also in other units related to parfum, there are similar situations and problems, such as the term "cream". From this we can see that the best definition of the word "cream", which is an author's product, is given in the Cambridge English Thesaurus dictionary. Examples of compound cases with `z are given. It is even enriched with illustrative examples. However, "Wordnet", "Longman", "Merriam Webster" dictionaries do not include a single unit related to the field of authorship.

Conclusion .As can be seen from these examples, the units related to attar were not collected enough by linguists, and the translation in different languages was not included in the electronic system by translators. Therefore, one of the urgent tasks facing linguists and lexicographers is to create a single dictionary of terms related to parfum, not only in English, but also in Uzbek, and develop fully universal electronic thesaurus dictionaries that are optimally used.

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